

A Ring-HEMT for Improved GaN MMIC Thermal Dissipation

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Abstract — A novel GaN HEMT which reduces the junction temperature is presented. The new structure uses a ring-like layout for the gate stripes, aimed at increasing the separation between stripes. Simulation and experimental results indicate improved performance of the *Ring-HEMT*, stemming from thermal effects and their interaction with device parameters. Compared to a regular HEMT, the new HEMT showed a decrease in junction temperature of 40°C from 178 °C resulting in a significant improvement in output power, and 43× fold increase in lifetime.

Index Terms — GaN HEMT, FET; Junction Temperature; Thermal Resistance; Reliability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microwave HEMTs (High-Electronic Mobility Transistors) and MMICs have performance which is generally limited by the maximum allowable voltage/electric field, current density, and junction (or channel) temperature. Self heating within the device is undesirable as it reduces performance and lifetime [1]-[2]. The junction temperature T_j is correlated with the device lifetime through the Arrhenius equation [3], and may be determined through simulations [4]-[6], theoretical models [7]-[8], or experiments [9]-[11]. Junction temperature directly affects the bandgap of the electronic material, carrier mobility, carrier saturated velocity, which in turn influence the device's pinch-off voltage, breakdown voltage, transconductance, saturation current, output power, and noise performance [12]. Reducing T_j typically leads to enhanced device performance, and reliable, sustainable operation. Self heating in transistors also leads to memory effects [13] which cause linearity performance degradation. Junction temperature is directly proportional to power dissipation through the thermal resistance value (which has some temperature dependence due to the nonlinearity of the thermal conductivity). It also depends critically on the device layout. In the case of field effect transistors (FETs) and high electron mobility transistors (HEMTs), T_j increases with the thermal resistance constant, and depends on the gate-width, gate-length, gate-pitch, and substrate thickness and

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Fig. 1. HEMT parameters description. Gate dimensions are $L_g \times W_g$, gate pitch s , substrate thickness is t .

Fig. 2. (a) Regular HEMT layout, showing two signal paths, (b) Ring-HEMT layout. Gate stripes are highlighted with a black line to show their locations.

thermal conductivity [8]. GaN-based power devices have demonstrated a high performance capability, yet their full microwave performance is still limited by thermal effect and its interaction with device parameters. A study on a new device layout was initiated to offer a different approach to address these thermal related issues. In this paper, a novel technique for reducing junction temperature is presented with experimental and simulation results. The technique focuses on re-arranging the gate-stripes into a ring-like layout, and increasing the separation among them, thereby reducing heat crowding. Simulations and experimental verification indicate a significant heat reduction as a result of the new design, leading to improvement in device microwave performance.

II. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION OF THE NEW HEMT

Consider a HEMT with constant highly localized heat sources (Fig. 1) on a substrate (say SiC) of thickness t . The heat sources represent the gates of the device with length, L_g , and width, W_g . The gate pitch is s , while thermal conductivity the material is k .

The junction temperature may be calculated using numerical analysis [6], or the closed form expression in [8]. The temperature in each stripe is determined by (a) the self heating of the gate stripe, and (b) the cross heating from

nearby gate stripes. Reducing the self heating can be achieved by increasing the gate length L_g , and decreasing substrate thickness, t , and power dissipation per millimeter gate-width, P_{mm} . However, in a typical fabrication process, L_g and t cannot be readily changed. Reducing P_{mm} by increasing power-added-efficiency is a well recognized goal [13]. Minimizing cross heating from neighboring stripes can be achieved by increasing the gate pitch, s . This comes at the expense of a larger device area, leading to (1) wider drain islands (hence, larger drain-source capacitance C_{ds}), (2) wider source islands (hence, greater source inductance L_s), and (3) increased phase difference of signal paths among the gate stripes (e.g., between path P_1 , and P_2 in Fig. 2). Increasing C_{ds} , and L_s usually reduces bandwidth, gain (due to negative feedback from L_s), and makes output matching more difficult. The phase difference also reduces output power and gain. These effects become more significant at mm-wave frequencies.

This paper proposes reducing junction temperature by rearranging the gates into a ring-like layout, Fig. 2. A regular HEMT with 0.25 μm gate length, 600 μm ($8 \times 75 \mu\text{m}$) gate periphery, 28.5 μm gate pitch, dissipating 6 W (30 V $\times$ 200 mA) is shown in Fig. 2(a). A Ring-HEMT with the same gate periphery, 600 μm , is shown in Fig. 2(b). As the Fig. 2(b) shows, the distance is maximized between the gates while keeping the paths length for all stripes roughly equal. The increase in the core area, compared to a regular HEMT, is about 50%. With the increased area, some of the internal capacitances are expected to increase. However, that may be tolerated in favor of a lower junction temperature, especially for wide bandgap semiconductors (such as GaN, and SiC) where the performance (gain, output power, and noise) is frequently limited by heat dissipation, not the intrinsic device capability. The temperature, T , and voltage, V , variation inside the device are similar in that both follow Laplace's equation. To reduce T (analogous to V), the heating elements (analogous to electric charges) should be distributed similar to electric charges on a conducting disk. For a conducting disk at a fixed voltage, the distribution of charge concentrates around the edges, as shown in Fig. 3(a). Ideally, the heating elements should be positioned in a similar way (less heating in the center, more at the edges) in order to achieve constant T (similar to constant V). This is what inspired the current layout.

A numerical simulator (ANSYS), with nonlinear thermal conductivity, was used to calculate the junction temperature for the regular HEMT, and the Ring-HEMT, Fig. 3(b), assuming a base plate temperature of 25 $^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature in the regular HEMT reaches 178.2 $^\circ\text{C}$, while the Ring-HEMT reaches 138.1 $^\circ\text{C}$, under the same power dissipation. That is equivalent to a 30% drop in thermal resistance which is very significant in terms of reliability [1]. Consider the Arrhenius equation:

$$\ln\left(\frac{MTF_2}{MTF_1}\right) = \frac{E_a}{k_b} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1}\right), \quad (1)$$

where $MTF_{1,2}$ is the mean-time-to-failure or (MTTF), E_a is the activation energy, $T_{1,2}$ are the absolute temperature in degree Kelvin, and k_b is the Boltzman constant (8.6×10^{-5} eV/K).

Fig. 3. (a) Charge distribution on a conducting disk at fixed voltage. (b) Channel temperature along center line for both regular HEMT (solid line), and Ring HEMT (dashed line).

Fig. 4. Pictures of a regular HEMT and a Ring-HEMT.

Fig. 5. (a) Change in cutoff frequency as the drain voltage is increased (the drain current was kept constant at 200 mA, 40% of I_{ds}). (b) Change in output power (P_{1dB}) as the drain voltage is increased.

Fig. 6. Sample power drive curves for a regular HEMT, and a Ring HEMT, $V_{ds} = 25$ V.

TABLE I
EXTRACTED EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT CAPACITANCES (PF/MM)

Type	C_{gs}	C_{gd}	C_{ds}
Reg. HEMT	0.710	0.14	0.09
Ring HEMT	0.711	0.23	0.14

Evaluating the expression for GaN with $E_a = 1.5$ eV [14], $T_1 = 138.1$ $^\circ\text{C}$, $T_2 = 178.2$ $^\circ\text{C}$, gives $MTF_2 / MTF_1 = e^{3.77} = 43.4$. That is, the improvement in lifetime is 43 $\times$ fold.

For a power amplifier (PA) MMIC, with the new device layout, the overall area of the MMIC would only increase slightly. Consider, for example, the layout of the

representative MMIC with dimensions 2.8×2.1 mm (area = 5.9 mm²). The active devices occupy about 0.22 mm², less than 4 % of the total area. Hence, even if the area of each HEMT was increased by 100%, the total increase in MMIC area would be around 4% only. An alternative approach to reducing the temperature is to increase the gate pitch. However, to achieve similar temperatures to those of the Ring HEMT, the gate pitch will need to be quadrupled and, consequently, the area will quadruple. Additionally, the paths length difference (e.g. between P_1 , and P_2 , Fig. 2A) will be severe, and the increase in C_{ds} , and L_s will be multi-fold.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs were fabricated to validate the new concept. The AlGaIn/GaN epitaxial layers were fabricated on MOCVD grown 3-inch semi-insulating 6H-SiC substrates. The material has an AlN nucleation layer on SiC substrates. The epitaxial layers consist of an un-doped GaN channel layer, an AlN barrier layer, an un-doped AlGaIn layer, and a GaN cap layer. Device isolations were formed by mesa etch using reactive-ion-etching (RIE). Ti/Al-based metal stack and RTA (Rapid Thermal Anneal) were used for source and drain ohmic contacts. Gate openings were defined by e-beam lithography.

Pictures of a regular HEMT and a Ring-HEMT are shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 5(a) shows the cutoff frequency f_i as a function of bias for the Ring-HEMT along with that of the regular HEMT. An approximate expression for the cutoff frequency is $f_i = g_m / 2\pi(C_{gs} + C_{gd})$, where g_m is the transconductance, C_{gs} is the gate-source capacitance, and C_{gd} is the gate-drain capacitance. As the figure indicates, f_i drops with drain voltage (the bias current is kept constant at 200 mA) due to heating, as expected. However, the rate of deterioration of f_i with bias is greater for the regular HEMT. Additionally, at full bias (30 V), the difference of f_i between the regular HEMT and the Ring HEMTs is insignificant. In fact, the Ring-HEMT slightly outperforms the regular HEMT. The equivalent circuit was extracted to find the internal capacitances. Table I shows the extracted capacitance values (per mm) of gate-source capacitance C_{gs} , gate-drain capacitance C_{gd} , and drain-source capacitance C_{ds} . The increase in capacitances is moderate. The growth of capacitances may be reduced through a revised layout. The Ring-HEMT and the regular HEMT were tested in a load-pull setup at 10 GHz. The load was optimized at 20 V drain voltage, and 40% I_{dss} for both devices; both have the same gate periphery and thus, the same drain current density. Then, the gate voltage and load were kept fixed to mimic HEMT use in a typical MMIC circuit. Fig. 5(b) shows the measured P_{1dB} , and Fig. 6 shows a sample power drive curve. At low bias (10 V), the output power for both HEMTs are similar. However, the regular HEMT's output power deteriorates quickly with drain voltage. The observed change in P_{1dB} is caused by heating, and the input/output matching variation with drain voltage and drive level, especially since the input/output capacitances of GaN HEMTs are known to be bias dependent. It should be noted that thermal and electrical effects are inter-related and determining the contribution of each is an open question for researchers. Both effects influence and provide feedback to each other. As the drain

voltage was increased, the power gain of the regular HEMT started to compress more than the Ring-HEMT.

The Ring-HEMT consistently outperforms the regular HEMT at higher biases. Three devices were measured of each type and similar improvements in performance were obtained.

IV. CONCLUSION

Currently, the full performance capability of GaN power devices is still limited by thermal effects and their effect on device parameters. In an attempt to stimulate further study to overcome this limitation without a substantial change in the fabrication processes, a novel device-layout technique for reducing heating in GaN HEMT structures was presented. The reduction in heating was numerically and experimentally demonstrated. The experimental results show great performance enhancements at 10 GHz. Over 3 dB increase in P_{1dB} is observed at 30 V bias. Although the exact improvement will vary from one process to another, in general the Ring-HEMT layout will reduce heating significantly. Transistor heating causes memory effects which degrade the linearity. Thus, it is expected that the Ring-HEMT will have better linearity performance. The technique was applied here to AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs. Nonetheless, it is equally applicable to HEMT and FET devices in other semiconductor materials (Si, GaAs, and SiC). High voltage (28 V) GaAs devices are particularly suitable for this technique given that heat is the main limiting factor for these devices.

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